

Table S1. Nucleotide sequences of primers used for real-time RT-qPCR amplification of cognitive impairment-related genes.

Gene	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (3'-5')	Amplicon size (bp)
<i>App</i>	CTGCTGACCGAGGACTGAC	CCGAACTCCGCATCCATCTT	94
<i>Bdnf</i>	ATTAGCGAGTGGGTACAGC	CGAGTTCAGTGCCTTTTGT	189
<i>Casp3</i>	ACCCTGAAATGGGCTTGTGT	ACAGGTCCGTTCGTTCCAAA	280
<i>Naa16</i>	AGTGCTACCGAAATGCCCTCA	TGTGTCTGGGCGTAACTGAAGA	139
<i>Psen1</i>	TGGTGTGGTCGGGATGATTG	CGACCAGCATAACGAAGTGGA	203
<i>Psen2</i>	CCTGGCGGTGATGGAATACA	AGCGCTTCCCACAGTATGAC	292
<i>Sor11</i>	CACCGTCTCATTGTCAGCAC	ATCTCGTAGCCCCTGGTTTC	123
<i>Syn1</i>	GCAGTTTGGTCATTGGGCTG	ACAGGGTATGTTGTGCTGCT	202
<i>Tmcc2</i>	TCCTCCTCTACCACCGATAACC	CTCCCTTGTCCACCCTTGTC	103
<i>Trkb</i>	TCGGTATCACCAACAGCCAG	GCTCGGGGCAGAGGTTATAG	141
<i>Zpr1</i>	GGATTACCCTCCACATCACAG	TGTCTTTCAGCAGTCCTTCG	153
Reference gene			
<i>Gdi</i>	CCGCACAAGGCAAATACATC	GACTCTCTGAACCGTCATCAA	159

Abbreviations: *App*, amyloid precursor protein; *Bdnf*, brain derived neurotrophic factor; *Casp3*, caspase 3; *Naa16*, N(alpha)-acetyltransferase 16, NatA auxiliary subunit; *Psen1*, presenilin 1; *Psen2*, presenilin 2; *Sor11*, sortilin related receptor 1; *Syn1*, Synapsin I; *Tmcc2*, transmembrane and coiled-coil domain family 2; *Trkb*, neurotrophic receptor tyrosine kinase 2; *Zpr1*, zinc finger protein 259.